

USEFUL STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING READING AND WRITING TO INTERMEDIATE AGE STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES

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Abstract: This article states that some strategies can be used for teaching reading and writing to intermediate age students with learning disabilities. In this research work, the author explains some beneficial tips while teaching reading and writing to these students with LDs.

Key words: strategy, reading, writing, intermediate, age, students, LDs, persistent Reading expands your concentration and your vocabulary. Reading exposes you to different writing styles. Reading helps you to subconsciously absorb syntax, grammar, style, and punctuation. Reading helps you to subconsciously absorb generic conventions, structure, and document design . Writing every day can benefit everyone, not only writers. It improves your memory, builds vocabulary, and refines your communication skills. Not to forget that writing can be very relaxing, especially if you lead a busy and stressful life. You can either start a dream journal, write down your daily adventures, or simply put the pen to the paper and see where it leads. There are no specific rules, just creating a habit of writing every day . If you are teaching some students with learning disabilities, how can you teach?

First, let's try to answer some questions what LDs, how many kids have learning disabilities (LD), what the prevalence of learning disabilities is in the world.

Learning disabilities are a common but often overlooked issue that affects a large number of people. It is important to understand the statistics and facts surrounding learning disabilities so that you can better understand the impact they have on individuals and the world.

For every 59 children, at least one has a single or several learning disabilities. As of 2021, 2.8 million kids are getting services involving special education. 4 million children younger than 18 have learning disabilities in the U.S. Children with learning disabilities account for 47% of the total amount of them receiving special education. Children with learning conditions have a 31% greater chance of being bullied than children with no disabilities. Moreover, learning disabilities (LDs) manifest in a number of different ways and with varying degrees of severity. For this reason, the following five tips may not apply to all students with LDs, however, they will have a positive impact on reading and writing acquisition for the majority of students. Take note of the following helpful tips:

Tip No. 1: Making Learning Accessible

Learning must be made accessible for intermediate students with LDs. An

intermediate student with reading LDs may read fewer than 100 words per minute, whereas the average student reads around 150 words per minute. Such a student may have persistent difficulty in identifying certain words. When students are asked to work on non-specific processing skills (e.g. summarizing, making inferences, making connections, etc.) using long written texts, students with LDs may immediately be at a disadvantage and often lack the time to complete the task.

In order to make learning more accessible for students with LDs, educators can:
Suggest that instead of a written text, a student use another medium for working on these skills, such as listening to a story being read aloud or watching a video;

Encourage students to work in pairs;

Encourage the use of assistive technology such as text-to-voice applications.

By offering various media from which to learn, instead of using written texts exclusively, educators can avoid creating obstacles to school success for students with LDs.

Tip No. 2: Strategies to Assist with Writing Tasks

According to Diane Wagner, LD@school expert, writing involves juggling many skills at the same time: grammar, spelling, letter formation, vocabulary, punctuation, capitalization, content, and following the directions of educators. All of these skills must be automatic for writing to be effective. As students move through to intermediate levels of schooling and beyond, the challenges relating to writing continue to increase; students become more involved in story writing, editing, research, note taking, and test/exam writing.

Students with LDs may experience writing difficulties related to handwriting (graphomotor difficulties) and/or written expression. It is important for educators to recognize where the breakdown in written language occurs, and to utilize appropriate and compensatory strategies.

Tip No. 3: Strategies to Assist with Spelling

Students with LDs often have persistent difficulty with spelling. Both French and English languages are complex; spelling is not always consistent nor is it always contextual. According to Jeffrey MacCormack and Nancy Hutchison, there are several strategies that have been found to be particularly effective for students with LDs, including:

Technology to instruct (e.g. spelling software)

Technology to compensate (e.g. spell-check)

Multi-sensory training (e.g. computerized spelling toys, Speak and Spell)

Study and word practice

Explicit teaching of spelling rules

Tip No. 4: Encourage Students to be Active Readers

Students with LDs have difficulty reading for a variety of reasons. For example, they may read too slowly, they may make frequent comprehension errors, they may have difficulty paying attention, or they may lack the motivation to read. Reading silently, on their own, struggling students do not have an opportunity to develop complex skills.

Fortunately, many practices are easy to use in an intermediate classroom:

Have students read a story in groups, in which each student “plays” a character; this will make reading more interesting and help the students to more fully understand the markers of dialogue;

Have students create a graphic organizer with the characters in the story and the connections between them. This will encourage students to take good notes and support reading comprehension.

Set the scene ahead of time, talking about the author and what he or she intended. This will spark the students’ interest, ensure that they all have the same knowledge going into the task, and enable them to understand the issues.

Caution students about any challenges they may encounter with the story, such as the use of flashbacks, long descriptive passages or a large cast of characters. This will keep struggling readers from tuning out, thinking that they are the only ones who find the story challenging.

Tip No. 5: Teach Reading Strategies

At the intermediate level, students are introduced to more varied and complex texts. The importance of reading strategies may not have been apparent to struggling readers earlier on, when the texts to which they were exposed were simpler. Educators can model strategies to understand what is being read before, during, and after reading and adapt these strategies to the type of text being read. By simply using effective reading strategies to support understanding, one can greatly impact school results.

To conclude, through the above recommendations, every teacher will be aware of the ways to teach English to students with disabilities quickly and easily. If you put these tips into practice, you will be able to engage your slow learner as well. Learning disabilities can negatively impact academic performance, but with proper accommodations and support, students with learning disabilities can still succeed in school. Learning disabilities are an important issue to be aware of and understand. By understanding the statistics and facts surrounding learning disabilities, we can better understand the impact they have on individuals and the world. With proper support and resources, students with learning disabilities can still reach their academic goals and achieve success.

References:

1. <https://www.ldatschool.ca/ask-the-experts-readingwriting>
2. <https://www.routledge.com/blog/article/how-reading-will-help-your-writing-and-add-pleasure-to-your-life>
3. <https://diymfa.com/writing/5onfri-five-benefits-of-writing-every-day>
4. <https://www.understood.org/en/articles/learning-disabilities-by-the-numbers>